

Business Intelligence

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Abstract

Business Intelligence systems combine operational data with analytic tools to present complex and competitive information to planners and decision-makers. Although business intelligence systems are widely used in industry, research about them is limited. Effective business intelligence systems must account for goal-oriented behavior and decision-makers.

Keywords : Analytical tools, Decision makers, Operational data

Introduction

Business Intelligence (BI) is crucial for the effective management and integral aspect of the decision- making processes for prudent companies attending to make use of a host of data relating to customer service, inventory, pricing so much more. Adoption of BI system has become one of the most significant technological and organizational innovations in a modern organization that promote knowledge diffusion and the cornerstone of business decision making.

Review of Literature

Tyson (1986) BI concentrates on gathering, process, and present information concerning customers, contenders, the business sectors, technology, and products.

Singh and Samalia (2014) BI is characterized as a framework which gathers, changes, and shows related information from various sources.

Objectives of the Study

For every work, there should be an aim. Like that, this study has the following purposes:

To develop the timeliness and quality of inputs to the decision process

To improve the capabilities available in the firm

To build its ability to offer a predictive analysis of data that relates to future occurrences.

Benefits of Business Intelligence

Faster reporting, analysis, or planning.

More accurate analysis, reporting, or planning.

- Better business decisions.
- I have improved data quality.
- I have improved employee satisfaction.
- I have improved operational efficiency.
- I have improved customer satisfaction.
- I have improved competitive advantage.
- Reduced costs.
- Increased revenues.
- Saved headcount.

What Does BI Do?

- Corporate performance management
- Monitoring business activity, optimizing customer relations, and traditional decision support
- Packaged standalone BI demands for specific operations or strategies
- Management reporting of business intelligence
- Creating forecasts based on historical data, past and current performance, and measures of the direction in which the future will go.

Functions of Business Intelligence

Features of business intelligence technologies vary by industry. The technology-driven process of business intelligence involves a variety of services, technology tools, applications, and methodologies that help a group collect data, prepare analyses, develop and conduct queries of databases, and create reports. Every function is used to maintain business decisions. Overall business intelligence is a data analysis process aimed at boosting company performance about its competitors by helping end-users within the company make more informed decisions.

Business Intelligence Trends

Currently, organizations are beginning to see that data and content should not be thought separate aspects of information management, but instead should be accomplished in an integrated enterprise approach. Enterprise information management makes business intelligence and enterprise content management together. Currently, organizations are going towards operational business intelligence which is presently underserved and uncontested by vendors.

Suggestion

Business Intelligence has a positive impact on an organization’s people as it does on performance, projects, and determinations. Business Intelligence is related to turn data into actionable information for leadership, organization, management, and decision making.

Conclusion

Many organizations are likely to opt for cloud-based BI in the future. In the end, informed declarations to enhance a company’s performance is extremely important. Business intelligence has all the necessary tools that make this happen.

References

1. <https://www.researchgate.net>
2. <https://www.investopedia.com>
3. <https://www.dataversity.net>